

Water Circularity Assessment Framework

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Abstract: In this study, a holistic water circularity assessment framework is developed and applied, coupling existing sustainability assessment approaches (i.e. Life Cycle Assessment - LCA and Material Flow Analysis - MFA) with hydrologic and nutrient cycle models, addressing current limitations for measuring circularity of water systems. The framework follows the systems approach, taking into account the interactions between the human managed and nature managed system, and considers the water, materials and energy pathways, enabling the assessment of the three circular economy - CE principles. The proposed methodology results in a set of physical, environmental and economic metrics and it is validated in an eco-touristic facility on a Greek island, where several circular water technologies are installed.

Keywords: Circular Economy; Water; Assessment Framework

Introduction: A paradigm shift is under way to replace linear models of water use that result in expensive and unsustainable end of pipe treatment and non-viable water abstraction rates with water management practices that adopt the circular economy principles. Methodological frameworks that holistically assess the circularity or circularity potential of water systems or components (i.e. closing water loops, waste elimination, natural capital regeneration, quality and economic value changes) are still missing. MFA has been extensively used to track materials as they accumulate and flow between systems and processes in industrial ecology and urban metabolism¹. However, standalone is not sufficient to assess and capture technological, environmental and economic changes in the value of water and the associated environmental impacts as water resources are exchanged between value chains or sectors. Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a powerful tool used to assess environmental impacts of products and services; however, its application in complex multifunctional circular water value chains with multiple outputs (i.e. water, energy, materials) and water uses is still challenging. Additionally, impact categories addressing aspects such as water scarcity and biodiversity are still based on high-uncertainty models². In this study, a holistic Water Circularity Assessment Framework is developed and applied to address the aforementioned limitations by coupling of MFA and LCA with hydrological, nutrient and carbon cycling models.

Methodology: The developed Water Circularity Assessment Framework is based on the realization of the three CE principles, i.e. “Regenerate natural capital”, “Keep resources in use” and “Design out waste externalities”, following the systems approach and taking into consideration the interactions between the human managed and nature managed system. The three different pathways, i.e. the water, materials and energy pathways, are considered in the analysis of the water system (Figure 1.1), resulting in a more holistic assessment. MFA is adopted in a hydrologic model that quantitatively and qualitatively maps all the input, output and stored flows for the water and materials pathways of the analysed system. Modified equations from the Urban Water Metabolism³ and the nutrients cycles – in this case the phosphorus cycle – are used in the model. A carbon cycle model is coupled to the hydrologic model in order to assess the carbon stocks and actual CO₂ emissions of the analysed water system. MFA is further used for the energy pathway and it is coupled with LCA enabling the assessment of the life cycle environmental impacts. The physical and environmental impacts obtained from the MFA-based and LCA-based models –

carefully considered to avoid double counting – are translated into economic benefits and costs and a set of indicators is developed, targeting each one of the CE principles enabling a holistic water circularity assessment.

Figure 1.1 CE principles and water, materials & energy pathways in Water Circularity Assessment.

Results & Discussion: The proposed Water Circularity Assessment Framework and the developed indicators are validated in the case-study of Tinos Ecolodge. The *maximum achievable self-sustainability potential* (MASSP) indicator shows that 73% of the total water requirements of the system can be met by alternative sources. The system meets 63% (i.e. the *actual self-sustainability* indicator, ASS) of the total water demands by alternative water sources, indicating a gap of 10% from the desired value. An additional 10% of the total used water is returned to the environment, indicating that 73% of the water loops are closed and it has the potential of increasing this percentage to 83% by equalizing ASS to MASSP. Regarding the phosphorus pathway, the produced phosphorus that could potentially be valorized covers 68% of the total phosphorus requirements. However, only 20% of these requirements is met by phosphorus recovery and utilization (i.e. *phosphorus self-sufficiency* indicator), indicating that the phosphorus loop is quite open.

Conclusions: A Water Circularity Assessment Framework has been developed, following the systems approach, considering the three CE principles and resulting in a set of physical, environmental and economic indicators, holistically assessing the circularity of current water systems. The benefit of the proposed framework is the coupling of MFA-based, LCA-based approaches and analytical models, overcoming the limitations from the standalone methods and enabling its use for future planning and decision support. The proposed framework was validated in Tinos Ecolodge, showing that 37% of the total water consumption is responsible for water withdrawals, while phosphorus requirements of the system are strongly related to extraction from natural sources (80% of the total requirements).

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program HYDROUSA (grant agreement No 776643).

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